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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 3

Pages: 340-347

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2965

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14750037

Manuscript Accepted: 12-10-2024

Acceptability of Locally Made Perfume and the Learners' Purchase Motivation

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the acceptability level of locally made perfume in terms of fragrance, price, packaging, health related consideration and purchase motivation of the learners. This also aimed to investigate the significant relationship between acceptability level of locally made perfume and the learners' purchase motivation. The researchers conducted a quantitative research study and used correlational research design. This study used simple random sampling as sampling technique as this used the one hundred-six (106) learners out of one hundred forty-five (145) of the total population of learners. The number of respondents were determined using Slovin's Formula. The study was conducted in Malalag Cogon National High School in the schoolyear 2024-2025. The researchers used mean and Spearman Rho as the statistical tools. The researchers conducted a pilot testing to test the reliability of the questionnaires and the results of the Cronbach's Alpha were good. Based on the findings, the acceptability level of locally made perfume is high, and the level of the learners' purchase motivation is high. Meanwhile, acceptability level of locally made perfume in terms of fragrance, price and health related consideration positively correlate in the learners' purchase motivation. On the other hand, acceptability level of locally made perfume in terms of price and fragrance positively correlate to each other. However, acceptability level of locally made perfume in terms of packaging negatively correlate in the learners' purchase motivation. In addition, the researchers recommended to improve the packaging of the perfume. Furthermore, the researchers recommended to increase the production of the locally made perfume in order to sell the product based on the high purchase motivation of the learners and the acceptability of the perfume.

Keywords: *ABM, locally made perfume, learners' purchase motivation, Philippines*

Introduction

Scent-seeking is not a relatively recent or unique occurrence. For thousands of years, people have used scent to change their surroundings for enjoyment and utility. The word "perfume" derives from the Latin "per fumum," which means "through smoke," and reflects its oldest application, which dates to the burning of aromatic woods and resins to flavor the air during religious ceremonies and rituals. The Egyptians employed fragrant compounds for embalming and placed rosemary bouquets in tombs to bless the eternal journey. The first known Chinese perfume objects are a pair of pomanders discovered in a tomb dating back to the sixth century BCE. The personal wearing of scent, or perfume, has its earliest documented use in Egyptian murals from the sixteenth century BCE (González 2018, Herz 2011, Olivia 2016 & Price, 2018).

Furthermore, solid perfume sales globally were valued at USD 1.65 billion in 2023 and are projected to reach USD 4.7 billion by 2032, expanding at a compound annual growth rate of 11.1% between 2024 and 2032. The expanding demand for personal care and fragrance products among consumers fuels the strong global fragrance sector. Technological developments in cosmetics and fragrances have changed consumer attitudes and usage of scent products. These fragrances, acclaimed for their uncomplicatedness and mobility, are an innovative creativity in the scent market, are drawing a lot of attention (Debadatta et al., 2024).

These scents also contribute to improving mood, enhancing physical appearance, and increasing self-esteem. Using perfume to treat headaches and insomnia is one of the less prevalent uses mentioned by some responders. The study's overall findings emphasize the importance of scent in Filipino consumers' grooming regimens. This study is the first attempt to understand the specific usage patterns and goals of perfume in the Filipino environment. As a result, its conclusions offer marketers and producers aiming to reach the Filipino market crucial information on the inclinations and driving forces of their target audience (Bansil, Canlas, Cruz, Del Rosario, Gonzales & Miranda, 2024).

In addition, the luxury goods sector in the Philippines is expected to reach USD 3.3 billion by 2022, making it one of the fastest-growing luxury industries in Southeast Asia. Perfumes are one of the most popular luxury goods categories among Filipino customers, out of all of them. Rising disposable incomes, shifting lifestyles, and a growing need for self-expression have all been linked to Filipino consumers' growing interest in luxury and designer perfumes. Not to mention that because of the rise of online influencers on numerous platforms, consumers are now more exposed than ever to the newest trends and styles in fragrances as well as all luxury goods in general (Dellyana & Ginting, 2023).

Furthermore, one theoretical tool that can help and motivate product developers and marketers is the three-factor benefits framework. By extension, the concept is especially useful for "scent marketing," which uses aromas to improve consumer reactions, purchase patterns, and perceptions of products. Marketing campaigns that manipulate scents can be classified as either intrinsic (added to the product) or ambient (occurring in the environment in which the product is evaluated). According to several studies, ambient fragrance

can improve both environmental and product evaluations (Bosmans, 2006; Fiore et al., 2000; Mitchell et al., 1995; Spangenberg et al., 1996).

Human interest in pleasant smells is ancient. Aristotle noted the aesthetic aspect of the smell sense by pointing out that it could be pleasurable even when the source neither protected nor nourished. In addition, Aristotle argued that pleasant smell could contribute to the well-being of humans. Later, the Roman poet Lucretius wrote that pleasant smell particles were smooth and round whilst unpleasant smell particles were barbed and prickly and invaded the senses by intrusive actions (Muchembled, 2020).

The study of perfumery is multidisciplinary activity which overlaps the molecular sciences – chemistry, plant biochemistry, with the humanistic fields – literature, advertising, fashion and aesthetics. The immensely successful and growing perfume industry has not, apparently, hit her to feel the need to examine the psychological phenomena underlying the effects of fragrance (Van Toller & Dodd, 2012).

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the acceptability level of locally made perfume and the learners' purchase motivation. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the acceptability level of locally made perfume in terms of fragrance, price, packaging and health-related consideration?
2. What is the level of the learners' purchase motivation?
3. What is the significant relationship between acceptability level of locally made perfume and the learners' purchase motivation?

Literature Review

Perfumes are liquid mixture of fragrant components dissolved in a suitable solvent such as ethyl alcohol. It is normally sprayed on the skin or clothes in order to get the fragrance smell through its vaporization and the vapors will reach the surroundings. So, vaporization of the perfume is an indication of the existence of the perfume and the rate of vaporization means the rate of getting the fragrance materials found in the perfume liquid solution. Impact, tenacity, diffusion and volume are important performance factors for the perfume. Tenacity is an indication of the lasting of the perfume after its application, it measures the persistence of a fragrance for long time near the evaporation source. Perfume is formulated by adding essential oils (concentrates) incorporated with ethanol and water and some fixatives. The concentration of the essential oils added depended on the type of the perfume made as shown in table. Tenacity is the gradual release or constant volatility of the perfume for long period of time. Many substances are used as fixatives to give the good tenacity of the perfume (Al-Bayati, 2016).

Evaporation of the fragrance materials in the perfume product is important. Fixatives is added to perfume solutions in order to obviate the difficulty of a series impressions of odor in the perfume because of different volatilities in the notes of the perfume, fixatives are substances of high boiling points and it will retard the rate of evaporation of the fragrances materials in the perfume, the fixatives give the perfume long time of lasting. There are different types of fixatives used in the formulation of perfumes such as; essential oils, animal secretions, synthetic chemicals and resinous materials. Ethanol can be assumed as a partially oxidized hydrocarbon. So, it is of interest to study the effect of different fixatives on the rate of evaporation of perfume formula made and to find the time of lasting to each fixative and the effect of the concentration of the mobile solvent (ethanol), the concentration of the essential oil on each type of fixative used. Four fixatives were used in the study, Sandalwood, Musk, and Glycerin and benzyl benzoate (Al-Bayati, 2016).

We read of how “femininity” is defined around body contours, and cosmetics, and how hormones are used by male-to-female transgenders. We go beyond the visual, reading about the importance of controlling or enhancing body odors among tour guides, who interestingly are especially concerned about the bad odor management of their foreign customers, using car perfumes to keep their work manageable and we learn how difficult it is for security guards to stay alert during their long shifts. Energy drinks and cigarettes help them perform their duties. All these transformations through what the French philosopher and historian Michel Foucault has called “technologies of the self” are as paradoxical as Palawan. On the surface, the products—which are technologies—seem to be mainly in the realm of the self but are, in reality, pushed, through marketing, from the outside, in contexts of inequality and exploitative labor relations (Hardon & Tan, 2017).

A sensual delight and an essential component of brand communication is fragrance. Fragrances are both a science and an art. Today, incorporating fragrant messages into products is difficult and depends on the skills of both chemists and perfumers (Pearlstone, 2022).

On the other hand, the sense of smell is social and cultural. People and other animals have a sense of smell and connect certain smells to certain memories. Smell is valued in certain cultures so highly that it is described with more adjectives than sights or sounds. Smell is a powerful emotional stimulant that is sometimes underestimated. In his book "Perfume: The Story of a Murderer," Patrick Suskind captivates readers not only with an intriguing plot but also with his ability to control a man's scent. The statement, "Odors have a power of persuasion stronger than that of words, appearances, emotions, or will," perfectly captures the empowering (Vasiliauskaite & Evans, 2019).

Also, we are interested in perfumery, an artistic subfield of smell, in this work. The process of creating perfumes involves mixing

several scent components, natural oils, and chemical molecules, creating a scent, a harmonic, fragrant whole. Since the beginning of recorded history of perfumery, which dates back to Mesopotamian times, "the Nose"—a specialist knowledgeable about complementary scent ingredients, their volatilities, odor longevity, and other factors—has been responsible for creating perfumes creating perfumes. This kind of knowledge is usually gained via years of training and experimentation with various component combinations (Vasiliauskaite & Evans, 2019).

Moreover, a perfume is a precise chemical formula created by the perfumer via years of trial and error with countless constituent combinations. Every perfume has a distinct scent because each one is made up of a particular combination of essential oils. After that, alcohol is added to dilute it and create cologne, eau de perfume, or eau de toilette. Notes are frequently used to describe perfumes. Notes are descriptions of aromas that are detected when a perfume is applied. Accords are multi-note compositions, particularly the well-known accords found in a wide variety of perfumes (Vasiliauskaite & Evans, 2019).

On the other hand, cosmetics' usage was widespread in antiquity, as a part either of daily life or of specific occasions, such as the burial of the dead and religious rituals. Perfumes in particular were very popular. They were first discovered in Mesopotamia, evolved in Egypt and then made their way to Greece (to the Minoans and Mycenaeans firstly) and the rest of the Mediterranean. They constituted a significant part of rituals, beauty, and commerce. People in antiquity believed that nice fragrances were associated with gods and had a positive effect on health and wellbeing as well as on the social contacts between them. The quality and quantity of a perfume was regarded as a social marker. Many ancient writers, such as Theophrastus, Pliny, Athenaeus, Hippocrates, Xenophon, Aristotle and others, provide several details about the ancient aromas. One thing that can't be doubted is that perfume (either with the form of incense or as oily extract from plants or, later, as a product of alcoholic distillation) has been a significant cosmetic product in all times (Voudouri & Tesseromatis, 2015).

Methodology

Research Design

A Correlational, quantitative research design was chosen to investigate acceptability level of locally made perfumes. The design was selected to gauge and characterize customers' present acceptance of locally manufactured perfumes. The desire of customers for locally created perfumes was taken into account during the course of this study. The researchers were able to present a clear picture of consumer sentiments towards locally created perfumes and provide insightful information for successfully promoting local products by employing a correlational research design (Anggarista & Wahyudin, 2022).

A study design known as correlational design was used to look at the relationships, which can happen on multiple levels, between or among two or more variables in a single group. This kind of non-experimental design looks at how two or more variables are related to one another. Keep in mind that the cause-and-effect link was not being tested by the researcher. Without influencing or modifying any of the variables, a correlational research design examines correlations between them. The direction and/or degree of the relationship between two or more variables were reflected in a correlation. A connection may have a positive or negative direction (Anggarista & Wahyudin, 2022).

Respondents

The researchers used the entire population of grade 11 and 12 learners. The researchers believed that these respondents were enough to provide sufficient data and information they needed. This way, researchers can be aware about the feedback of their product. Since the study used correlational research design, the data from respondents was gathered through printed survey questionnaires.

But before they undergo survey, researchers discussed about the research ethics by keeping their identity private and safe, to avoid misconduct and misinterpretation. Before acquiring response from the respondents, researchers asked their permission first if ever they agreed in conducting a survey to them or not. Getting also the permission from the adviser of the respondents and from the principal was vital in the study. Researchers got approval from the adviser and principal to follow the ethics in research.

Instrument

The researchers created their own questionnaires in gathering data. The constructed questionnaires are based on the related literature read by the researchers. The researchers include questions that are related to the topic. The researchers construct a question to know whether the fragrance, price, and packaging influences the learners' purchase motivation or if the health consideration affects learners' purchase motivation in buying the perfume.

After constructing the questionnaires, researchers got their approval from their adviser to advance in the next step which was to go under validation process. Also, according to Carling and Mjelva (2021), having the approval of the experts also help on assessing a good survey questionnaire. In order to also attain a good data to interpret and analyze.

The research instrument used undergone pilot testing to ensure the reliability of the questionnaires. The data gathered by pilot testing was computed using Cronbach's Alpha. The result of the statistics was excellent with a mean of 0.96. This means that the research instrument was reliable and easy to comprehend.

Improving the accuracy of a survey is the focus of Mark S. Litwin's book, which shows how to assess and interpret the quality of survey data by thoroughly examining the survey instrument used. He explains how to code and pilot test new and established surveys. In addition, he covers issues such as: how to measure reliability (including test-retest, alternate form, internal consistency, inter-observer and intra-observer reliability); how to measure validity (including content, criterion and construct validity); how to address cross-cultural issues in survey research; and how to scale and score a survey (Carling & Mjelva, 2021).

A successful data collection survey is much more than a set of well-designed questions that are written down and administered to a sample population. There are good surveys and bad surveys. Bad surveys produce bad data that is, data that are unreliable, irreproducible, or invalid, or that waste resources. Good surveys, on the other hand, can yield critical information and provide important windows into the heart of the topic of interest (Carling & Mjelva, 2021).

Procedure

The data collection process for this study was separated into distinct phases in order to address the researchers' clarification of the problem. In choosing the respondents, first, the investigators define the target population who are relevant in their study. Before proceeding in acquiring data from respondents, researchers undergone asking permission and approval from school head and advisers of the respondents in order to avoid unethical issues and protect the privacy of the respondents.

But before obtaining information from them, researchers discussed first the importance of research ethics. It simply said to keep what is confidential to avoid misconduct. Respondents in this study undergone terms and conditions before answering every question and giving their feedback. They may also give their recommendations to be the base for researchers in adjusting the product.

The research adviser suggested and approved survey questions as the first step. After that, the research questionnaires submitted to validation process. The selected samples provided with the link by means of a designated representative for each section. The researchers now proceeded with the data gathering stage. This functioned as the subsequent stage, which involved gathering data from respondents. The third phase were summarized by content and document analysis of the gathered data. The creation of statistics and the computation of all the data included in the final stage.

The locally developed perfume was made of the following materials: Dipropylene Glycol (DPG), Fixative, Fragrance Oil, Distilled Water and Ethyl Alcohol. First step in developing locally made perfume was preparing the measuring materials such as graduated cylinder, beaker, cup, bottles and stirring rod. The locally made perfume was developed from 20% of dipropylene glycol, 20% fixative, 30% fragrance oil, 80% of distilled water and 20% of ethyl alcohol. After that, the finished product undergone fermenting process. Fermenting process took 1 week before testing the locally made perfume.

Process of developing perfume:

1st step: Prepare the materials.

2nd step: Put 70% distilled water in the cup. Measured using graduated cylinder

3rd step: Add 20% of ethyl alcohol. Measured using graduated cylinder.

4th step: Add 20% of dipropylene glycol. Measured using graduated cylinder.

5th step: Add 30% of fragrance oil. Measured using graduated cylinder.

6th step: Stir thoroughly the mixture using the stirring rod.

7th step: Then, add 20% of fixative to make the perfume long lasting. Measured using graduated cylinder.

8th step: Stir the mixture.

9th step: Transfer the mixture to clean bottles.

10th step: Preserve the developed perfume for 1 week.

Data Analysis

This study used Spearman Rho correlation in computing the collected data.

The Spearman rank correlation has been known for over a hundred years to applied researchers and methodologists alike and is one of the most widely used non-parametric statistics. Still, certain misconceptions can be found, either explicitly or implicitly, in the published literature because a population definition for this statistic is rarely discussed within the social and behavioral sciences (Astivia & Zumbo, 2019)

A Spearman correlation coefficient is also referred to as Spearman rank correlation or Spearman's rho. It is typically denoted either with the Greek letter rho (ρ), or rs. Like all correlation coefficients, Spearman's rho measures the strength of association between two variables. As such, the Spearman correlation coefficient is similar to the Pearson correlation coefficient (Jia, Yang, Zheng, Zhu, and

Bi 2020).

Results and Discussion

This section tackles the interpretations of the collected data. Below are tables of mean of variables with its indicators and the significant relationship between the variables.

There are three (3) tables below which are about locally made perfume acceptability, learners' purchase motivation and the significant relationship between the acceptability level of locally made perfume and learners' purchase motivation. Locally made perfume has four (4) indicators: fragrance, price, packaging and health-related consideration. Learners' purchase motivation has only one indicator namely, purchase motivation. The third table shows the significance on the relation of locally made perfume and the learners' purchase motivation.

Table 1. *Locally Made Perfume Acceptability*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Fragrance	3.98	High	Agree
Price	3.99	High	Agree
Packaging	3.81	High	Agree
Health-Related Considerations	3.98	High	Agree
Overall	3.92	High	Agree

Shown in the table 1 is the acceptability of locally made perfume with the following indicators: fragrance, price, packaging and health related consideration. The four indicators generated an overall mean of 3.92 which can be interpreted as high. This means that the learners agree that they accept the locally made perfume. Among the four indicators, price got a highest mean of 3.99 which can be interpreted as high. This means that the learners agree on the acceptability of locally made perfume in terms its price. Meanwhile, health-related consideration attained a mean of 3.98 which can be interpreted as high. This means that the learners agree on the acceptability of locally made perfume in terms its health-related consideration. Additionally, fragrance obtained a mean of 3.93 which can be interpreted as high. This means that the learners agree the acceptability of locally made perfume in terms its fragrance. Lastly, packaging got a mean of 3.81 which can be interpreted as high. This means that the learners agree the acceptability of locally made perfume in terms its price.

The results of the study supported the findings of Levrini and Jeffman (2021) in which their research found out that it was clear that the differences between the sensorial responses and the cognitive actions (especially when prices are disclosed). Sensorial responses suggested consumers' preference for premium brand, which indicated that smell, texture, and color of this product were considered better than the others.

Table 2. *Learners' Purchase Motivation*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Purchase Motivation	3.85	High	Agree
Overall	3.85	High	Agree

Shown in the table 2 is the level of learners' purchase motivation. The purchase motivation generated a mean of 3.85 which can be interpreted as high. This means that the learners agree that they are motivated to purchase the locally-develop perfume.

This is in congruence to the study of Auf, Meddour, Saoula and Majid (2018) who found out that multiple factors in the background are playing a crucial role in influencing customers towards making their final decision. Hence, it is extremely important for the marketing department to comprehend the factors that impact customers' buying processes and decision-making. This paper empirically examines the correlation between price, motivation, perceived cultural importance, and their influence on consumer purchasing behavior. Consumers' preferences have been changing over time as trends and fashions evolve, but researching consumer buying behavior can uncover these preferences, aiding marketing managers in adapting their strategies accordingly.

Table 3. *The Significant Relationship Between the Acceptability of Locally Made Perfume and the Learners' Purchase Motivation*

<i>Locally Made Perfume Acceptability</i>	<i>Learners' Purchase Motivation</i>
	<i>Purchase Motivation</i>
Fragrance	0.3327* (0.0016)
Price	0.4169* (0.0001)
Packaging	0.0271 (0.8032)
Health-Related Consideration	0.2728* (0.0106)

Table 3 presents all the indicators measuring the acceptability of the locally made perfume has a significant relationship to the learners' purchase motivation except for the packaging. It could also be noted from the results that three of the indicators of acceptability of

locally made perfume in terms of fragrance, price and health-related consideration are positively correlated with the indicator of learners purchase motivation since all of the p-value is lesser than 0.05. However, one of the indicators of acceptability level of locally made perfume namely, the packaging, is not significantly related to purchase motivation since the p-value is greater than 0.05. Among all the indicators of acceptability of locally made perfume, price got a highest r- value of 0.4169. Meanwhile, fragrance obtained an r- value of 0.3327, health-related consideration attained an r- value of 0.2728 and packaging got an r- value of 0.0271.

The results of the study supported the findings of Auf, Meddour, Saoula and Majid (2018) in which price and purchasing behavior are influenced by the decisions made, but other factors, like brand loyalty, price insensitivity, and testimonials, can also have an impact. When two products are equally attractive, consumers consider whether a promotion is available to help them decide which to buy. It was discovered that price frames have an impact on consumers' perceptions of the promoted price and the value that the products carry at the promoted price. Prior research has demonstrated how pricing affects customer purchasing decisions.

Furthermore, the study supported the findings of Levrini and Jeffman (2021), price is considered one of the most important attributes in consumer's choice. On the other hand, consumer's knowledge about price tends to be imprecise. The study showed how conscious price variable was the major influence in their purchase intention.

The study supported the findings of Latina, Sordan, Calamba and De Jesus (2022), in their study believed that fragrance marketing was a powerful tool that may affect consumers' intents to buy if it evoked strong feelings about the surrounding aroma. It is important to be aware of the emotional reactions that fragrance employed in marketing might evoke in consumers since it may provoke particular emotional reactions. The study's emotional response focuses on how the ambient aroma improves the mood, emotions, and comfort level of its customers. Emotional and redolent characteristics: Odor-evoked events have a major impact on mood and lead to physical correlations of different emotional states, suggesting that they can be useful in generating sales for companies that have perfected the craft of manipulating the ambient scent of their physical store.

The results negate the study of Lee (2021), on average, each tested perfume contained ten chemicals identified as sensitizers, which can trigger an allergic reaction. On average, each tested perfume contained four chemicals recognized for disrupting human hormones. This hinders consumers from understanding the potential negative health impacts of the perfume.

Lastly, the results supported the findings of Salem (2018), the findings show a relationship between the independent variables (i.e. visual packaging design, verbal packaging design, and packaging benefits) and the dependent variable (i.e. consumer purchase decision) based on several reasons discussed thoroughly in this paper.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following are the conclusions:

The acceptability level of locally made perfume is high. Thus, the learners agree the acceptability level of locally made perfume in terms of fragrance, price, packaging and health-related consideration.

The level of purchase motivation is high. Thus, the learners agree that they are motivated to buy the locally made perfume.

There is a significant relationship between all of the indicators of acceptability level of locally made perfume in terms of fragrance, price and health-related consideration and the learners' purchase motivation except the packaging.

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